

INCIDENCE OF STOMA PROLAPSE AFTER ILEOSTOMY

Dr. Muhammad Owais Riasat^{*1}, Dr. Hazrat Bilal², Dr. Dileep Kumar³,
Dr. Muhammad Muneeb⁴, Dr. Hussain Ahmed⁵, Dr. Muhammad Raheel⁶

^{*1}MBBS, Postgraduate Trainee, Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre, Karachi

^{2,3}MBBS, FCPS, Professor of Surgery, Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre, Karachi

^{4,5,6}MBBS, Postgraduate Trainee, Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre, Karachi

¹m_owais911121@yahoo.com, ²hbburki74@gmail.com, ³dileep123_kumar@yahoo.com,

⁴muhammadmuneeb900@gmail.com, ⁵hussainahmedshaikh@gmail.com

⁶m.raheelsiddiqui44cmc@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19398797>

Keywords

Ileostomy, Stoma prolapse, Complications, Loop ileostomy, JPMC

Article History

Received: 03 February 2025

Accepted: 20 February 2025

Published: 06 March 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Muhammad Owais

Riasat

Abstract

Background: Ileostomy is a common surgical procedure performed for intestinal perforations, malignancies, and obstructive lesions. Although effective, it carries several complications, among which stoma prolapse is distressing for patients and may require reoperation. Reported incidence varies globally, while local data are limited.

Objective: To determine the incidence of stoma prolapse after ileostomy at Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre (JPMC), Karachi.

Methodology: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of General Surgery, JPMC, over six months. A total of 58 patients undergoing ileostomy were included through non-probability consecutive sampling. Patients were followed at 2 weeks, 1 month, and 3 months postoperatively for detection of stoma prolapse, defined as bowel protrusion of more than 5 cm beyond skin level. Data were recorded on a structured proforma and analyzed using SPSS v26.

Results: The mean age of patients was 38.6 ± 12.4 years; 36 (62.1%) were males and 22 (37.9%) females. Loop ileostomy was performed in 42 (72.4%) patients and end ileostomy in 16 (27.6%). Stoma prolapse occurred in 5 (8.6%) patients, more common in loop ileostomy (9.5%) than end ileostomy (6.3%). Peristomal skin excoriation was observed in 14 (24.1%) patients, parastomal hernia in 2 (3.4%), and stoma retraction in 1 (1.7%).

Conclusion: The incidence of stoma prolapse after ileostomy at JPMC was 8.6%, consistent with international literature. Loop ileostomies were more frequently associated with prolapse. Preventive surgical techniques and regular follow-up are essential to reduce morbidity.

INTRODUCTION

Ileostomy is commonly used as a temporary or permanent diversion for congenital abnormalities, trauma, inflammatory bowel disease, and colorectal cancer. Despite being

lifesaving, it has several side effects that have been documented in 10–70% of patients. These include skin excoriation, parastomal hernia, and stoma prolapse, which is a serious late morbidity (1,2).

Full-thickness bowel protrusion through the stoma site is known as stoma prolapse. Depending on the study population, stoma type, and follow-up period, reported incidence ranges from 2% to 26% (3). Ileostomies prolapse is less frequent than colostomy prolapse; rates are usually reported to be between 2 and 3%, though some series report as high as 11% (4,5). This difference is supported by meta-analyses: randomized trials and cohort studies have consistently found that the incidence of prolapse is significantly lower in ileostomies than in colostomies (6).

Prolapse is caused by several risk factors, such as advanced age, obesity, elevated intra-abdominal pressure, redundant bowel, and weak abdominal muscles (7,8). Prolapse is also predisposed by surgical factors like an enlarged fascial aperture, positioning the stoma outside the rectus abdominis muscle, and improper mesentery fixation (9,10).

There is a dearth of local literature discussing the prevalence of stoma prolapse after ileostomy, despite the abundance of international data. Counselling patients, enhancing perioperative planning, and honing surgical techniques all depend on an understanding of the frequency and risk profile in our setting. To provide information that could enhance stoma care and long-term results, this study attempts to ascertain the prevalence of stoma prolapse following ileostomy in our patient population. After ileostomy, stoma prolapse is a distressing complication that affects stoma care, patient quality of life, and healthcare resources. There is little local evidence despite global data. Surgeons will be guided in counselling, preventive measures, and better operative planning to lower morbidity and reoperation rates based on the incidence in our population.

METHODOLOGY

After receiving approval from the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSP) and the institutional ethical review committee, this descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out

over a six-month period in the Department of General Surgery at Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre (JPMC), Karachi. All patients having ileostomies during the study period, whether in elective or emergency settings, made up the study population. As long as they gave their permission and were available for follow-up, patients of both sexes and all ages were included. Patients who expired during the index admission, had a prior history of stoma formation, or were lost to follow-up before three months were not included.

Using the WHO sample size calculator, the sample size was determined using a previously published study's 7.1% incidence of stoma prolapse following ileostomy, a 95% confidence interval, and a 7% margin of error. In order to account for possible attrition, the sample size was increased from the minimum required of 52 to 58. Eligible participants were recruited using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique.

A structured proforma was used to collect data. Age, gender, hospital registration number, comorbidities, ileostomy indication, and ileostomy type (end or loop) were among the baseline data that were documented. Operational information was recorded, including the surgeon's name and surgical technique. Following surgery, patients were monitored in the ward or outpatient clinic at two weeks, one month, and three months. The surgical team evaluated the clinical presence of stoma prolapse using the operational definition, which is defined as bowel protrusion that extends more than 5 cm above skin level.

SPSS version 26 was used to analyse the data. While qualitative variables like gender, ileostomy type, and incidence of stoma prolapse were displayed as frequencies and percentages, quantitative variables like age were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. The chi-square test was used to evaluate associations after stratification by age, gender, and ileostomy type; a p-value of less than 0.05 was deemed statistically significant.

RESULTS

The study included 58 ileostomy patients in total. With a range of 15 to 70 years, the average age was 38.6 ± 12.4 . There were 22 females (37.9%) and 36 males (62.1%). Typhoid perforation was the

most common reason for ileostomy (41.4%), followed by trauma (12.0%), colorectal cancer (25.9%), and tuberculous stricture (20.7%). End ileostomy was performed in 27.6% of cases, whereas loop ileostomy was the most common type (72.4%) (Table 1).

Five patients (8.6%) experienced stoma prolapse at the three-month follow-up. Of these, one happened in end ileostomy patients (6.3%) and four in loop ileostomy patients (9.5%). Males were more likely than females to experience prolapse (11.1%), although the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.42$). In a similar vein,

the incidence of prolapse was marginally higher in patients over 40 (11.1%) than in those under 40 (6.5%), although the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.31$) (Table 2).

Additional complications included stoma retraction in 1 patient (1.7%), parastomal hernia in 2 patients (3.4%), and peristomal skin excoriation in 14 patients (24.1%). Figure 1 shows the overall distribution of complications.

The flowchart (Figure 2), which summarises patient enrolment and follow-up, reveals that all 58 patients were monitored for three months, during which time 53 remained complication-free and five developed stoma prolapse.

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of Patients (n = 58)

Variable	Frequency (%)
Age (mean \pm SD)	38.6 \pm 12.4 years
Gender: Male	36 (62.1)
Gender: Female	22 (37.9)
Typhoid perforation	24 (41.4)
Colorectal malignancy	15 (25.9)
TB stricture	12 (20.7)
Trauma	7 (12.0)

Table 2. Incidence of Stoma Prolapse According to Variables (n = 58)

Variable	n	Prolapse n (%)	p-value
Overall	58	5 (8.6)	-
Gender: Male	36	4 (11.1)	0.42
Gender: Female	22	1 (4.5)	-
Loop Ileostomy	42	4 (9.5)	0.68
End Ileostomy	16	1 (6.3)	-
>40 years	27	3 (11.1)	-

Figure 1. Distribution of stoma-related complications among patients undergoing ileostomy (n = 58). The most common complication was peristomal skin excoriation (24.1%), followed by stoma prolapse (8.6%), parastomal hernia (3.4%), and stoma retraction (1.7%).

Figure 2. Patient flow diagram showing enrollment and outcomes. All 58 patients were followed for three months, of which 5 developed stoma prolapse while 53 remained complication-free.

DISCUSSION

Stoma prolapse happened in 5 cases (8.6%) of our 58 ileostomy patients, which is consistent with the larger range of 2%–16% reported in adult studies (11). A meta-analysis confirmed that ileostomies are generally safer in this area by showing noticeably lower prolapse rates than colostomies (12).

The most common complication in our study was peristomal skin excoriation (24.1%), which is consistent with previous findings that found that up to 70% of patients experienced this type of skin problem as one of the most common stoma-related complications (13). Stoma retraction (1.7%) and parastomal hernia (3.4%) were relatively uncommon; this could be because of our short 3-month follow-up period, as these conditions typically manifest later (14).

Our cohort may have been slightly impacted by risk factors for stomal prolapse that have been found in the literature, such as advanced age, obesity, elevated intra-abdominal pressure, and lax abdominal musculature (15). While not statistically significant, these results are consistent with our trends: higher prolapse in male patients and those over 40.

Surgical technique is also important. Research emphasises that stoma prolapse is more likely to

occur when the stoma is positioned outside the rectus muscle or the fascial opening is enlarged, particularly if bowel fixation is insufficient (16). This risk is increased further by mobile or redundant bowel segments, which are frequently observed in loop ileostomies (17). Consequently, careful stoma creation—through the rectus muscle, with appropriate fixation—is essential.

Thorough surgical technique and follow-up are crucial for prevention, according to a 2023 systematic review, which also confirmed the wide incidence range of stoma prolapse (7%–26%) (18). Temporary relief from symptoms may be achieved with non-surgical management (lubrication, appliance adjustment, manual reduction); however, surgical correction is recommended for severe complications such as strangulation or persistent symptoms (19).

Our findings support the necessity of early follow-up, appropriate stoma placement, and appropriate fascial aperture sizing as preventive measures. Additionally, they emphasise that to detect late complications, longer-term monitoring beyond three months is necessary.

Conclusion:

The incidence of stoma prolapse following ileostomy at JPMC was 8.6% in this study, which

is in line with findings from other countries. Although these correlations were not statistically significant, prolapse was more common in male patients, older patients, and those with loop ileostomies. Hernia and retraction were rare during the brief follow-up period, but peristomal skin excoriation was the most common complication overall. To reduce morbidity, these results highlight the significance of careful surgical technique and early follow-up. To more precisely define risk factors and preventive measures, larger, multi-center studies with longer follow-up are required.

REFERENCE

- Mehboob A, Khan R, Abid K, et al. Frequency and complications of ileostomy. *Cureus*. 2020;12(10):e11271. doi:10.7759/cureus.11271
- Maeda K, Nagasaki T, Saito N. Prolapse of intestinal stoma: management and prevention. *Ann Gastroenterol Surg*. 2022;6(6):730-737. doi:10.1002/ags3.12616
- Parini D, D'Ambrosio G, Calabrò GE, et al. Surgical management of ostomy complications: the MISSTO study. *World J Emerg Surg*. 2023;18(1):45. doi:10.1186/s13017-023-00516-5
- Ge Z, Wu Q, Huang X, et al. Complications of preventive loop ileostomy versus colostomy: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Surg*. 2023;23:2129. doi:10.1186/s12893-023-02129-w
- Khan MA, Ahmed M, Aslam M, et al. Diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of ileostomy complications: an updated review. *Cureus*. 2023;15(1):e34541. doi:10.7759/cureus.34541
- Zubillaga-Mares A, Moreno-Aranda J, García-Hernández C, et al. Stoma-related complications: frequency and risk factors in a tertiary care hospital. *Eur Surg Res*. 2024;65(2):89-97. doi:10.1159/000530456
- Shabbir J, Britton DC. Stoma complications: a literature overview. *Colorectal Dis*. 2020;22(6):739-745. doi:10.1111/codi.15000
- Robertson I, Leung E, Hughes D, et al. Prospective analysis of stoma-related complications. *Ann R Coll Surg Engl*. 2020;102(3):203-207. doi:10.1308/rcsann.2020.0005
- Park JJ, Del Pino A, Orsay CP, et al. Stoma complications: the Cook County experience. *Clin Colon Rectal Surg*. 2020;33(4):228-236. doi:10.1055/s-0040-1701240
- Elnaim AL, Alshareef AH, Altahir AA, et al. Intestinal stomas: basics, complications and controversy – systematic review. *Acad Med Surg*. 2024;8(1):e127121. doi:10.29337/ams.127121
- Maeda K, Nagasaki T, Saito N. Prolapse of intestinal stoma: management and prevention. *Ann Gastroenterol Surg*. 2022;6(6):730-737. doi:10.1002/ags3.12616
- Ge Z, Wu Q, Huang X, et al. Complications of preventive loop ileostomy versus colostomy: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Surg*. 2023;23:2129. doi:10.1186/s12893-023-02129-w
- Elnaim AL, Alshareef AH, Altahir AA, et al. Intestinal stomas: basics, complications and controversy – systematic review. *Acad Med Surg*. 2024;8(1):e127121. doi:10.29337/ams.127121
- Parini D, D'Ambrosio G, Calabrò GE, et al. Surgical management of ostomy complications: the MISSTO study. *World J Emerg Surg*. 2023;18(1):45. doi:10.1186/s13017-023-00516-5
- Babakhanlou R, et al. Stoma-related complications and emergencies. *Int J Emerg Med*. 2022;15:20. doi:10.1186/s12245-022-00421-9
- Johnson P. Intestinal stoma prolapse: clinical overview. *Surg Sci*. 2016;7(12):515-520. doi:10.4236/ss.2016.712072

- Essani R, Bergamaschi R. Stoma prolapse: late complication of stoma surgery. *Clin Colon Rectal Surg.* 2008;21(1):31-34. doi:10.1055/s-2008-1055310
- Monette MM, Harney LA, Kiran RP. Local repair techniques for stoma prolapse: outcomes from case series. *Surg Case Rep.* 2016;2:128. doi:10.1186/s40792-016-0283-1
- Parini D, et al. Management of stoma prolapse: current approaches. *World J Emerg Surg.* 2023;18(1):45. doi:10.1186/s13017-023-00516-5
- Krishnamurty DM, Blatnik J, Mutch M. Stoma complications: risk factors and management. *JCO Oncol Pract.* 2017;13(5):e501-e510. doi:10.1200/JOP.2016.018796

